

MSDS-OPP: Operator Procedures Prediction in Material Safety Data Sheets

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Abstract—The digitalization and tracking of products across the supply chain is one of the challenges of Industry4.0. The collected historical data contains crucial information about their constitution and safety constrains. Material Safety Data Sheets (MSDS) are the main source of information of safety issues about products. However, they have incomplete information, which causes operator confusion, that could be critical in some situations. The usage of multi-label text classification and Natural Language Processing (NLP), would make easier the information retrieval and allow the prediction of the material procedures, given the other MSDS fields. For that, it was built the Material Safety Data Sheet Operator Procedures Prediction Tool (MSDS-OPP), which scrapes MSDS from the web, extracts topics from the files, processes the textual data and using multi-label text classification predicts which will be the operator procedures. The results prove that both text processing pipelines and text classifier perform well with nice values of precision, recall and F1-Score. In general, the tool has their limitations, but for operator recommendations would be a good solution, giving some traces about the steps to perform.

Index Terms—Natural Language Processing, Material Safety Data Sheets, Text Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Industry4.0 is emerging as new industrial parading, allowing the manufacture of customized products (smart manufacturing), the monitorization of the industrial process, or the shop floor resources optimization [1]. The actual trend is to digitalize the shop floor equipment, enabling the understanding of the industrial process. The data collection process focuses on associate to each product the corresponding data allowing the product tracking and the visualization of their historical data. The historical data allows the identification of futures product defects and the estimation of patterns according to that defects. To complement these data normally is added some information about safety issues and danger materials presents in the composition of the final product. These materials have restrictions and dangers to the operator usage and handing; normally, this information has the format of a text document.

A Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS) [2] is the standard text document that describes in a detailed way the material ingredients, the health hazards, the emergency procedures, and other fields. This document has a standard structure, with a clear description, to be easily readable by the operators in case of an emergency. These fields can be grouped into categories such as chemical data, health hazards, personal

operator protection, and operator procedures. Usually, the MSDS's have as main representant the chemical products due to the MSDS structure; however, in the other industries, the usage of a standard document, like the MSDS, would help to understand the dangers of a particular product.

The main limitation for the usage of MSDS as a primary source of information from a material is the variance between documents written by different companies. This variance difficult the document understanding and, in extreme cases, allows the MSDS structure mutation according to each company. A solution to address this restriction is an approach based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) that automatically extracts the knowledge from an MSDS and generates the procedures to the operator take in case of an emergency.

An approach based in NLP and Machine Learning (ML), would allow the usage of incomplete information (e.g., the MSDS only has the ingredients data or the health hazards), which is common due to the different material manufactures and concern on share information in the MSDS data [3]. Additionally, these processed data could be annexed to the product historical data, allowing the users/operators to access these data independently of their role in the supply chain (e.g., operator, transporter or consumer). In certain situations, it's mandatory to have a quick response by the operator, performing a set of actions to neutralize that danger. The description of the material procedures needs to be clear about the steps to complete and always available. Additionally, the search engine must have a quick response time to avoid any delay in the operator actions.

The development of the Material Safety Data Sheet Operator Procedures Predictor (MSDS-OPP) pretends to accomplish those goals. This tool scrapes the MSDS from the web, extracts each section from the MSDS file, processes the text, and predicts the several procedures (fire fighting, material storage, or material disposal). More concretely uses multi-label text classification to predict the procedures, associating one classifier to each one (fire fighting, storage, and disposal). The classifier input features are extracted from the chemical data, health hazards, and personal protection categories, using NLP algorithms. These algorithms filter the tokens and n-grams from the text and convert that textual data to numerical arrays to feed the classifier. The classifier labels are transformed from the procedures text description (also present in the MSDS file)

to binary class labels, using a parallel pipeline different from the one used in the features.

The main contributions of the MSDS-OPP are 1) the scrapping of MSDS files from the web, due to the difficulty of obtaining that data (not very common or in some cases paid); 2) the extraction of knowledge from the data sheets, that could help the operator searching for MSDS fields; and 3) the operator procedures prediction, which allows a quick prediction of the steps to perform in situation of fire, material storage or material disposal.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The MSDS's are a source of information about dangerous products in several sectors like the medical, the industrial, or the agricultural. An automatic approach to analyze that data would benefit these sectors. However, before start deploying models and NLP pipelines, it's useful to understand the problem and the data itself. The data analysis must focus on the MSDS structure, validating which sections are significant for the problem and which procedures have the potential to be useful for the operator needs. After that, the analysis must focus on similar works in the area regarding the gaps existing in the literature.

A. Background

Across the literature [3] [4] exist a discussion between what an MSDS should contain. The typical structure includes eight different sections: 1) Chemical Identity and Source Data, 2) Hazardous Ingredients, 3) Physical and Chemical Characteristics, 4) Fire and Explosion Hazard Data, 5) Reactivity Data, 6) Health Hazard Data, 7) Precautions for Safe Handling and Use, and 8) Control Measures. Table I presents a more detailed view of the data that provides from each section. There each row contains a subsection, with their data type (e.g., textual, numerical, boolean) and their category.

To easily understand the content of an MSDS, Table I contains a reorganized structure, split into four different categories of data 1) chemical, 2) health hazards, 3) personal protection, and 4) operator procedures. The chemical data includes information about the ingredient constitution of the material; it also contains other chemical properties like the boiling point, the vapor density and pressure, the flash point, or the evaporation rate. Additionally, it contains short descriptions of the material appearance and decomposition products. The health hazards category includes the carcinogenicity specifications, a description of the effects of overexposure, and a short explanation of other health hazards. The personal protection data defines the equipment needed to handle the material; in this case, it specifies the gloves, eyes, and respiratory equipment to use. It also contains information about the ventilation in the area and some additional precautions to take in care. The last category is the operator procedures; here, it's specified the protocol to take into account in some situations. These situations could be emergencies like fire or some other casual actions like material storage or disposal. Due to emergencies, it's essential to have a tool that quickly given the material returns the emergency

procedures to make by the operator. Additionally, as shown in Table I, it's also specified the manufacturing company and the product name as general information data.

TABLE I
MSDS STRUCTURE

Subsection	Data Type	Grouping Category
product name	text	general info
company name	text	general info
ingredients	text	chemical data
decomposition products	text	chemical data
materials to avoid	text	chemical data
vapor pressure	numeric	chemical data
vapor density	numeric	chemical data
boiling point	numeric	chemical data
flash point	numeric	chemical data
evaporation rate	numeric	chemical data
material appearance	text	health hazards
carcinogenicity	text	health hazards
effects overexposure	text	health hazards
first aids	text	health hazards
eyes protection	text	personal protection
respiratory protection	text	personal protection
protective gloves	text	personal protection
ventilation	text	personal protection
protective equipment	text	personal protection
fire fighting	text	operator procedures
storage precautions	text	operator procedures
disposal procedures	text	operator procedures
spill procedures	text	operator procedures

Although the current structure has its limitations, such as their ambiguity, that often causes delays in diagnosing the occupational diseases, which places a further risk to the operator to develop long-term disorders [3]. Another constraint is the omission of vital information regarding the protected formula as a trade secret. In particular cases, the information is underestimated, such as the flash point [5], where one-third of the products have a lower flash point value than the specified in the MSDS. The underestimation of the flammability of the product can cause severe problems, like ignitions. Furthermore, the little information about diseases associated with the product represents a lack for material usage. Regarding that, the MSDS is a useful starting point for handling some emergencies such as chemical contamination [4].

B. Related Work

As related work, the focus was to identify the typical approaches used in the MSDS analysis. Most of the works related to MSDS focus on their structure and limitations [3] [4] [5] [6], alternatively other publications emphasis the search engines and databases used to manage the MSDS [7] [8]. In general, there are a few publications that use an NLP or ML approaches to analyze an MSDS dataset; the most similar ones focus on the drug side effects analysis [9] [10] [11] and text classification in general [12] [13] [14].

The MSDS availability is a concern, usually, the traditional organizations/repositories that manage that data are the Registry of Toxic Effects of Chemical Substances (RTECS), the Hazardous Chemicals Data Base (HSDB) or the Occupational Safety & Health Administration (OSHA) [8]. With the growth

of the Internet, some search engines like *Google* or *Yahoo* allows quick access to the MSDS data. Nevertheless, these data could be irrelevant, incomplete, or even false, which makes then not 100% trustful [7]. To avoid these situations have emerged some specialized sites/repositories that provide reliable and free data, like the *msdsonline.com* or the *hazard.com*.

In the universe of applications of NLP and ML methods, one of them is the drug indications and side effects prediction. The PISTON [9] allows the prediction of drug indications and side effects using topic modeling and Natural Language Processing (NLP). This tool extracts relations between drugs, genes, and diseases from literature data, finding sentences when both terms co-occur (topic) and compute their probability. The resulting probability values construct a drug-topic probability matrix. On top of the matrix is built a classifier that predicts the indications and side effects of drugs. Also, in this sector, NLP methods are used to automatic map drug product labels in the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA) [10].

NLP tools are the core of decision support systems [11] that assist the human decision providing useful information about the problem. In both industrial and medical environments, it's crucial to make decisions with all the knowledge about the issue. Mainly, in medical situations is essential to identify the right risk factors, new treatments or medications, and associate concepts with certain diseases [11], for that a tool that predicts an initial guess will accelerate the process of diagnostic and treatment of diseases. Translating to the industrial applications, some situations like emergencies (e.g., fire) or daily work tasks (e.g., material storage), would benefit from the usage of these tools [14].

Text classification allows the label of documents according to several categories, it could be used to label federal reports, movie reviews, or cooking recipes. The process typically starts with a dataset of labeled documents; these documents provide features that feed the classifier to predict which label fits well. There are variants for the steps used in the document classification pipeline. The classifier could use weight terms according to the term relevance [12]. The representation of the features could mutate depending on the implementation; in some situations, it is preferable to use the typical bag-of-words image; other representations are the words embedding or the graph embedding [12] [13].

In general, these NLP works don't focus on the MSDS analysis, and the publications based in the MSDS center on their structure and limitations. Most of the time, they use a human hand analysis, which delays the process. Also, these approaches are human dependent, which difficult the adaptability of new operators to the shop floor when they need to handle these products. One of the alternatives to accelerate the analysis process is the usage of NLP methods for the knowledge extraction and ML techniques to the operator procedures prediction. This additional tool would help both operators or physicians, given them supplementary information about the material. Their usage would increase the infrastructure/factory productivity, and add further details about the product safety issues, to their historical data.

III. METHODOLOGIES

The MSDS-OPP allows the prediction of the operator procedures for disposal, storage, and fire situations. To accomplish these goals, the MSDS-OPP performs most of the steps of an end-to-end NLP project. The tool architecture, in Figure 1, starts with the data acquisition from the web, then using text processing techniques extracts the features and class labels, with them, train one classifier to each procedure, and finally reconstruct the classifier output to a procedure description. In more detail the MSDS-OPP architecture has five different stages: 1) the data scrapping, that gets the MSDS files from the web; 2) the feature extraction, which extracts features from the MSDS files and applies NLP methods to feed the classifiers with clean data; 3) the label transformation, that converts the label procedure text description in a set of class labels, which are used as targets to train and validate the classification model; 4) the classification models, which implements and validates different classification models to predict the operator procedures; and 5) the description reconstruction, that given the predicted class labels transforms these tuples in a standard description of the procedures.

A. Data Scrapping

MSDS files are hard to find on the web; in most cases, the user needs to pay for the dataset. Because of that, the MSDS-OPP scrapes the dataset from the site *hazard.com*. There are stored many different types of data sheet files; the MSDS-OPP uses the *F2* data sheet type, which is well structured and easy to scrape. The repository stores the files grouped in HTML "folders", which are composed of links each one associated with one MSDS file. So each HTML page contains a set of links parsed using the *beautiful soup* framework, which makes easier the link parsing. Using the MSDS file link, it's downloaded the page from the repository and converted from HTML to a text file. This process is iterative searching all the links present in each folder; for the HTTP requests, it's used the *urllib* framework.

The scraped data contains 236500 data sheet files, which corresponds to 1.3GB; the folder structure is the same present in the repository. That's huge among of data, which allows the usage of deep learning algorithms for the classification process.

B. Feature Extraction

The feature extraction part is one of the stages where are applied the NLP techniques. These techniques allow a generic and robust extraction of features from the original text. To efficiently implement these methods is used a pipeline structure, where each algorithm is a step in the pipeline, and the data flows throw all the steps.

Before applying the NLP pipeline, the MSDS sections described in Table I are extracted from each file using regular expressions. To accelerate the extraction is adopted a multi-processing approach, dividing the MSDS files by *N* workers. The mined sections converge to a table, where each row corresponds to one document. Then the parts associated with

Fig. 1. MSDS-OPP Architecture

the chemical data, health hazards, and personal protection categories are transformed into input features for the classifiers.

The pipeline implemented to transform an input text in a set of numerical features to feed the classifier applies a sequential process using different methods in each step, Figure 2. First, the characters pass to lower case, and it's used a tokenizer to transform the plain text in a collection of word tokens. Next, a filter removes the stop words and the punctuation from the terms collection. From them are built one-grams and bigrams based on the term frequency. Then the tokens collection is vectorized into a matrix with the tokens vocabulary as columns, and each row containing the number of occurrences of a token in the respective document.

The next step in the pipeline is the transformation of the number of occurrences of each token in the *term frequency-inverse document frequency* (TF-IDF) matrix. This method allows the understanding of how vital is a term in a particular document. The term frequency (TF) component calculates the fraction between the number of times that a token appears in a document and the total number of terms in the document. The inverse document frequency (IDF) calculates the ratio between the total number of documents and the number of them containing the token. The TF-IDF is the product of both term frequency and inverse document frequency, where the IDF is constant to each term, and TF is variable between documents. This statistical method allows a term-weighting approach that reflects the importance of a term in a document.

The result of the entire pipeline is a matrix that has the terms vocabulary as columns and the term weight associated with each document as rows. From that matrix are selected the 150 more relevant terms, which feed the classification model,

like features.

C. Label Transformation

The label transformation uses a different approach due to the limited number of class labels. Here the MSDS dataset provides a text description as a procedure, which isn't a binary label understandable by the classifier. For that, the procedure description text mutates into a set of labels that the classifier uses as targets. The transformation pipeline contains methods like Name Entity Recognition (NER), Position Tagging (POSTAG), or Syntactic Dependency (DEP).

The label transformation, as the feature extraction, consumes text data obtained by regular expressions, in specific the operator procedures sections. Due to the usage of a classifier per procedure, it's mandatory to have a label transformation pipeline per each one. Mainly because each classifier has different labels, according to the procedure (e.g., the label "use air supplied rescue equipment" for the fire fighting procedures classifier and the label "incinerate absorbed material" for the disposal procedures classifier).

The label transformation pipeline, Figure 2, starts with the tokenization of the text description. For each sentence are extracted their entities and noun-chunks (noun plus words describing the noun). The extraction of noun-chunks allows a more ambiguous search for the key terms of the sentence. The repeated terms are filtered between the entities and the noun-chunks, resulting in a new set of tokens. Based on the extracted terms, the sentence is retokenized, the resulting tokens are tagged using position tagging, and it's analyzed the syntactic dependencies. Then for each entity and noun-chunk is checked their dependency tag; if it's an attribute

or a direct object (*obj*), it's extracted the subject from the sentence and added to the relation, with the entity or noun-chunk. If the dependency tag is an object of a preposition (*obj*), the extracted relationship is the entity/noun-chunk plus the previous prepositional modifier.

Fig. 2. Feature Extraction and Label Transformation - NLP Pipelines

As a result, the pipelines produce a set of relations, from them, are selected the 20 more frequent. That relation will be the labels of the classifier, used for the classifier training, and their predictions validation.

D. Classification Models

After extracting both features and class labels from the MSDS file, it's applied a text classifier to predict the MSDS operator procedures based on the input features (chemical data, health hazards, and personal operator protection). The current structure subdivides into three different classifiers, each one associated with one procedure. This approach allows the specialization of each model in a particular procedure. On the other hand, the usage of only one classifier, which generalizes for the three procedures, could be a wrong choice due to the complexity of the problem. The usage of three classifiers fits well in this problem, because it's required a concrete answer to each procedure, with one classifier the solution mixes the three procedures description, which can cause some confusion in the operator. Each classifier activates different class labels for the same input, due to the multiple steps to perform for some products. This classification problem fits in the multi-label classification, which is a generalization of the multi-class classification, that can assign various labels to the same instance.

The classification models tested for the procedure prediction were the Decision Tree (DT) and the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). Decision Trees (DT) are an intuitive and straightforward method, supported in both single-label and multi-label classification problems. The algorithm uses a tree structure where the internal nodes are conditions related to the features; the condition answer splits into branches, that could be other conditions or in case of end node the decision. Other of the algorithms that allow multi-label classification is the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), which groups the data in the more similar N clusters using the distance between instances. As model hyper-parameters, the DT classifier uses the default values of the *scikit-learn* framework; the KNN classifier uses 15 k-neighbors, which is a proximal value to the number of labels.

E. Description Reconstruction

The description reconstruction component is critical, considering the operator must understand the predicted procedure. The output of the classifier is an array of tuples, which usually it's hard to know by the operator. To the operator understand this information clearly, it's added an extra step that receives the classifier output and transforms it into a standard sentence comprehensible by the operator.

The easiest way to perform this task was re-using the description sentences that generate the class labels. So, during the process of label extraction, from the description of the procedure, it was associated with each label the most common sentence that generates it. So, the result is an association between a sentence (step description) and the relation tuple (classifier label), that maps the classifier output to a clean procedure step description. Even though the simplicity of this approach, it allows the description reconstruction, maintaining the generalizing capabilities of the label extractor.

IV. RESULTS

After describing the architecture and mechanisms of the MSDS-OPP tool, it's time to perform a set of tests to validate those functionalities and compare them with the existing ones. Initially were evaluated the three procedures predictors, testing different classification models for each one. The metrics used to assess the different classification models are the recall, the precision, and the F1-score. Additionally, it was measured the area under the ROC curve (AUC), to confirm the previous metrics. The second study focus on an end-to-end analysis of the fire fighting procedures predictor. The process was analyzed, starting with the features and labels analysis, building a bag-of-words model, allowing the visualization of the total number activation in both features and labels.

A. General Results

The overall results have the aim to evaluate each classifier's performance. For that, the considered performance metrics were the precision, the recall, the F1-score, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC). Due to the large dataset size, for the evaluation purposes, only 10% of them it's required, which corresponds to 23000 MSDS files. From the partial dataset, 70% was for training the algorithms, and the rest 30% for the test set. Figure 3 shows the obtained results for the three procedures predictors (fire, disposal, and storage), where each one was validated using two different classification models, the Decision Tree (DT) and the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). The graph on top shows the comparison between the F1-score and the area under the curve (AUC); the bottom graph compares the precision and recall.

The graph analysis shows that the procedure with more accurate predictions is the fire fighting predictor, and the worst is the storage predictor. This discrepancy in the results reflects the complexity associated with each procedure prediction. Due, the typical steps associated with the correct procedures, e.g., the phrase "dispose in accordance with the federal laws" is one of the most commons steps to perform according to

Fig. 3. Classifiers Comparison

the disposal procedures. Regarding the constraint, the overall results are acceptable, with an F1-score near to 0.65 and an AUC of 0.75. Even though these values are far from 1, they are satisfactory due to the complexity of the class labels and the problem itself.

Focusing in the difference between the classification models performance, the overall results are pretty similar regarding the F1-score and the AUC. In terms of precision-recall analysis, the button graph shows that the Decision Tree algorithm has an equalized value of precision and recall. However, the K-Nearest Neighbors algorithm has more discrepant values with high values of precision and lower values of recall. These results reflect that the KNN algorithm classifies only the high probability true positives instances, ignoring the less probable true positives, which results in a more precise algorithm. Regarding that outcome, the classification model to use may depend on the situations if the operator wants a more precise set of steps to perform uses the K-Nearest Neighbors, otherwise if he wants an initial guess or a recommendation for the actions of the procedures uses the Decision Tree algorithm.

B. Fire Fighting Results

The overall classification results only validate the tool superficially. Based on that knowledge, a more detailed study of the whole process would help to understand their gaps and constraints. That analysis considers the fire fighting procedures classifier that uses a Decision Tree as a classification model.

The first analysis to make is checking the output from the features extraction pipeline and the label transformation pipeline. Both are present in Figure 4, where the graph on the top has the 20 classes used by the classifier, and in the button,

there is a bag-of-words representation of the most common words used as features by the classifier. Also, the target data graph shows the performance metrics (precision, recall, and F1-score) associated with each class. The performance metrics indicate that some of the classes have results near to 1.0, while the others have results around 0.5 and 0.6. Additionally, some of the class labels denote more complex relations (e.g., "full protective equipment" or "inhalation smoke") than others (e.g., "contact skin"). The class distribution is unbalanced, having the first classes more instances, which isn't a constraint due to the stable values of precision and recall. The data used for the bag-of-words representation was from the training set, and the metrics provide from the test set.

The feature data has a more explicit form, most of the time represented by one or two words. Concerning that, the features are standard for the three predictors; some of the terms have more weight depending on the predicted procedure (e.g., the tokens "water" and "ventilation" are more related to the fire fighting procedures prediction).

V. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

Summarizing, the MSDS-OPP allows a quick response to the steps of the procedures to perform by the operator in certain situations. The tool permits the automatic acquisition of MSDS's from the web, and extraction of essential components from those files, making more straightforward and reliable the information retrieval. This way, the user, operator or not, have an additional tool that helps in their decisions and improves their quality of work. Regarding the results, the MSDS-OPP performs with satisfactory values of precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC, using both classification models (DT and KNN). The usage of two classification models allow to specify if he wants a more precise algorithm (KNN), returning only the more probable steps to perform, or a more balanced one (DT).

Nevertheless, this tool has its constraints; one of them is the duplication of information between the features and the targets, generating some bias in the results. As a partial solution, the process of information extraction from the MSDS was improved, making the regular expressions more accurate, and the class labels more precise. Although, the multiprocessing implementation, the MSDS-OPP can accelerate its predictions, optimizing mainly the label transformation component.

As future work, one of the goals is to predict more types of operator procedures (e.g., spill procedures), making the MSDS-OPP more reliable and generic for a significant number of situations. Also, finding patterns that associate the MSDS structure/writing style with possible errors would help to rectify potential issues like the flash point underestimation. In terms of implementation, it's good to validate different approaches, testing different classification models in the MSDS-OPP. Still, in the case of the text processing, there are some alternatives to be explored, like word embedding. Additionally, the procedures reconstruction uses a fundamental approach to perform this task, the utilization of other options, like autoencoders, could perform better.

Fig. 4. Fire Fighting Procedures Classifier Features and Labels Bag-of-Words

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